

Human Reference Atlas

Standard Operating Procedure

Authoring Crosswalk Tables Between Functional Tissue Unit Illustrations and ASCT+B Tables

Naming and organizing document layers in Adobe Illustrator, assigning ontological terms to anatomical structures and cell types, and compiling SVG and crosswalk table files

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Introduction

This SOP covers procedures for formatting, naming, and organizing 2D functional tissue unit (FTU) illustrations in Adobe Illustrator and linking their anatomical structures and cell types to relevant entities in the ASCT+B table.

The overall process of mapping FTU illustrations to ASCT+B tables involves the following steps:

- selecting a 2D FTU illustration,
- setting up the basic file structure,
- separating cells by type to correspond with the ASCT+B table; and
- creating an SVG file and a crosswalk table.

The primary audience for this SOP is Indiana University project personnel who are creating crosswalk tables for FTUs in the Human Reference Atlas. Those who would like to understand how these crosswalk tables are constructed may also find this SOP of interest. This SOP assumes a basic working knowledge of Adobe Illustrator.

Roles and Responsibilities

The **Principal Investigator (PI)** approves budgets associated with FTU illustration construction, sets high-level goals and associated deadlines, attends meetings, and reviews notes and recordings from relevant meetings between the Medical Illustrator, Subject Matter Experts, and other key personnel as needed.

The **Biological Consultant** validates the crosswalk tables to ensure 2D reference object nomenclature is consistent with ASCT+B tables. They also work closely with the System Architect to upload crosswalks to the release GitHub repository for use in HRA releases.

Human Reference Atlas

Standard Operating Procedure

The **SVG and Crosswalk Table Author** validates the illustrations and performs cell segmentation on the images. Once the illustrations are finalized, they convert the Adobe Illustrator file to an SVG file and create a crosswalk table.

The **System Architect** works with the Biomedical Consultant to upload crosswalks to the appropriate GitHub repository for inclusion in HRA releases.

Role	Name	Email
Principal Investigator (PI)	Katy Börner	katy@iu.edu
Biomedical Consultant		
SVG and Crosswalk Table Author	Supriya Bidanta	sbidanta@iu.edu
System Architect	Bruce W. Herr II	bherr@iu.edu

Table 1. Roles, names, and email addresses of key personnel.

Procedures

Selecting a 2D functional tissue unit illustration

- A 2D FTU illustration is designed following the instructions covered in the SOP titled [Creating 2D Illustrations for Functional Tissue Units \(FTUs\)](#). Selection is based on the FTU name used in the Human Reference Atlas Anatomical Structures, Cell Types and Biomarkers (ASCT+B) table and the folder name in which the illustration is kept. An example is given in **Fig. 1**. Organ-specific anatomical structures and cell type names match those in the ASCT+B table.

Human Reference Atlas

Standard Operating Procedure

Figure 1. Thymus lobule FTU illustration in Adobe Illustrator.

Setting up the basic file structure

- Open the FTU illustration in Adobe Illustrator. Confirm that the illustration has been flattened (Layers menu -> Flatten Artwork). Name this layer Art.
- Select the entire Art layer. Choose Ungroup from the Object menu (Object -> Ungroup) to ungroup any grouped artwork.
- Go to Object -> Expand Appearance to convert any brush strokes into editable shapes.
- Confirm that labels have been applied to representative cells of each type using the terminology listed in the relevant organ-specific Anatomical Structures, Cell Types and Biomarkers (ASCT+B) table of the Human Reference Atlas. It is important that the labels already identified in the ASCT+B Table are used in the crosswalk table and that no new cell type names are introduced unintentionally.
 - Create a new layer at the top of the layer stack named Labels. Move existing labels here, or create new labels using these guidelines:
 - Use Inter Regular font (an open source font available at <https://rsm.me/inter>), size 16, to label each ASCT+B table entry using the names in the 'CT/<x>/LABEL' column (where x is the level).
 - The first word of each term should be capitalized. Labels may run onto multiple lines when appropriate for visual clarity. The label text should be left-justified.
 - Use straight 1-point leader lines at 90- or 180-degree angles. Leader lines consist of a single 1-point black line 1 pixel above a 1-point white line and appear on top of the anatomy where they overlap the illustration.

Human Reference Atlas

Standard Operating Procedure

Separating cells by type to correspond with the ASCT+B table

- Use the Pen tool (P) to create a shape that outlines the area representing an individual cell or group of cells of the same type (see **Fig. 2**). Edit this shape with the Direct Selection tool (A) until you are satisfied with the outline.

Figure 2. Grouping each cell present in the inset of FTU illustration by anatomical structure or cell type.

- Unlock the Art layer. Select the shape and go to Objects -> Path -> Divide Objects Below. This should divide the editable shapes you have created by expanding the illustration components when setting up the basic file structure.
- Using the Selection Tool, select the divided components. Cut (X) the selection and Paste in Place (Shift+Command+V) on a new layer. Label this layer to correspond with the ASCT+B table cell type represented.

Human Reference Atlas

Standard Operating Procedure

Figure 3. Segmentation of anatomical structures and cell types in an FTU.

- Continue making selections and moving cells to this shared layer until you have selected all cells for each cell type. Check your work by selecting each layer and visually checking the bounding boxes (black in the example for Blood_Vessel_Endothelial_Cell, **Fig. 3**) for each layer, or by turning layer visibility on and off.
- The knife tool (K) may be used as an alternate method for cutting illustrations into separate cell types. This method is slightly faster but less accurate, in that you cannot edit the knife path after the cut has been made.
- Delete the empty Art layer. The illustration should now be fully separated into labeled cell type layers.
- Save the 2D illustration as an Adobe Illustrator (AI) file.

Creating an SVG file and a crosswalk table

Convert the 2D illustration AI file into an SVG file and record the details of each anatomical structure and cell type in a table referred to as the crosswalk table.

- To convert the AI file to an SVG file, first install the Inkscape tool found at <https://inkscape.org>.
- In Adobe Illustrator, go to File -> Export -> Export As.
- In the pop-up window, select for the options shown in **Fig. 4**.

Human Reference Atlas

Standard Operating Procedure

Figure 4. AI file to SVG file conversion options.

- Once the SVG file is loaded in Inkscape, select XML Editor (Edit -> XML Editor).
- The right side of the tool will have sections and layers that are created in SVG.
- Select the correct layer and expand the selection.

Human Reference Atlas

Standard Operating Procedure

Figure 5. A sample SVG file that maps each anatomical structure and cell type present in the 2D FTU illustration to its organ-specific ASCT+B Table entry.

- Download the latest [asct-b-2d-models-crosswalk table](#). The most recent (and all previous versions) of this table can be found in the publicly available catalog of all HRA digital objects (<https://lod.humanatlas.io/2d-ftu/>).
- Select each element individually and fill in the existing crosswalk table with representative details. There is a single crosswalk table that includes all FTUs.

Crosswalk table column header	Column contents	Description of column contents
organ_label	Organ name	Organ name
Organ_id	UBERON_ID	UBERON ID of the organ
Anatomical_structure_of	FTU name	FTU name
Source_spatial_entity	#2DRefObjects	This code denotes which illustration this crosswalk

Human Reference Atlas

Standard Operating Procedure

		pertains to. It is used by the System Architect.
Node group	XML id created using inkscape tool	The columns are the variable that helps to map it from SVG to the JSON-LD file used in the FTU explorer
Node name	XML id created using inkscape tool	
label	label from .AI file	
ontologyID	from ASCT+B table	
representation_of	ontology link	The purl id of the cell type. For example: http://purl.obolibrary.org/obo/CL_1000324
exist_asctb:	boolean (0/1) If 0 then CT/AS is absent in ASCT+B Table, 1 otherwise	Use 0 in cases where we do not have any cell type specific to the functional tissue unit, but it is shown in the illustration. Use 1 in cases where the cell type or anatomical structure is present in the ASCT+B table and is illustrated in the illustration
type	CT/AS	CT - Cell type AS - Anatomical structure
REF/1	First reference	
REF/1/ID	DOI link/details	
REF/1/NOTES	Publication reference (for example: doi: 10.3390/jcm7030054)	
REF/2	Second reference	

Human Reference Atlas

Standard Operating Procedure

REF/2/ID	DOI link/details	
REF/2/NOTES	Publication reference (for example: doi: 10.3390/jcm7030054)	
Inset (if any)		Insets are magnified regions of large functional tissue units. For instance, in Fig. 5 the case of the Thymus, the larger FTU has two insets.

Table 2. Description of the content in each column of a crosswalk table.

- Continue until all elements from the SVG have been populated in the crosswalk table named "asct-b-2d-models-crosswalk".
- Deliver the crosswalk table to the Biomedical Consultant so it can be added to the [Human Reference Atlas Portal](#).
- The Biomedical Consultant saves this crosswalk as a CSV and adds links to the appropriate files to the HRA portal which is housed in the CNS GitHub repository.

organ_label	organ_id	anatomical_	source_spat	node_group	node_name	label	OntologyID	representation_of	svg file of si	exist_asctb	type
Thymus	UBERON:00023 #FTUThymusLoi #2DRefObjects	Double_Positive	Double_Positive	double-positive,	CL:0000809	http://purl.obolibrary.org/obo/CL_0000809	2d-ftu-thymus-th	1	CT		
Thymus	UBERON:00023 #FTUThymusLoi #2DRefObjects	Double_Positive	Double_Positive	double-positive,	CL:0000809	http://purl.obolibrary.org/obo/CL_0000809	2d-ftu-thymus-th	1	CT		
Thymus	UBERON:00023 #FTUThymusLoi #2DRefObjects	Double_Positive	Double_Positive	double-positive,	CL:0000809	http://purl.obolibrary.org/obo/CL_0000809	2d-ftu-thymus-th	1	CT		
Thymus	UBERON:00023 #FTUThymusLoi #2DRefObjects	Double_Positive	Double_Positive	double-positive,	CL:0000809	http://purl.obolibrary.org/obo/CL_0000809	2d-ftu-thymus-th	1	CT		
Thymus	UBERON:00023 #FTUThymusLoi #2DRefObjects	Double_Positive	Double_Positive	double-positive,	CL:0000809	http://purl.obolibrary.org/obo/CL_0000809	2d-ftu-thymus-th	1	CT		
Thymus	UBERON:00023 #FTUThymusLoi #2DRefObjects	Double_Positive	Double_Positive	double-positive,	CL:0000809	http://purl.obolibrary.org/obo/CL_0000809	2d-ftu-thymus-th	1	CT		
Thymus	UBERON:00023 #FTUThymusLoi #2DRefObjects	Double_Positive	Double_Positive	double-positive,	CL:0000809	http://purl.obolibrary.org/obo/CL_0000809	2d-ftu-thymus-th	1	CT		
Thymus	UBERON:00023 #FTUThymusLoi #2DRefObjects	Double_Positive	Double_Positive	double-positive,	CL:0000809	http://purl.obolibrary.org/obo/CL_0000809	2d-ftu-thymus-th	1	CT		
Thymus	UBERON:00023 #FTUThymusLoi #2DRefObjects	Double_Positive	Double_Positive	double-positive,	CL:0000809	http://purl.obolibrary.org/obo/CL_0000809	2d-ftu-thymus-th	1	CT		
Thymus	UBERON:00023 #FTUThymusLoi #2DRefObjects	Double_Positive	Double_Positive	double-positive,	CL:0000809	http://purl.obolibrary.org/obo/CL_0000809	2d-ftu-thymus-th	1	CT		
Thymus	UBERON:00023 #FTUThymusLoi #2DRefObjects	Double_Positive	Double_Positive	double-positive,	CL:0000809	http://purl.obolibrary.org/obo/CL_0000809	2d-ftu-thymus-th	1	CT		
Thymus	UBERON:00023 #FTUThymusLoi #2DRefObjects	Double_Positive	Double_Positive	double-positive,	CL:0000809	http://purl.obolibrary.org/obo/CL_0000809	2d-ftu-thymus-th	1	CT		
Thymus	UBERON:00023 #FTUThymusLoi #2DRefObjects	Double_Positive	Double_Positive	double-positive,	CL:0000809	http://purl.obolibrary.org/obo/CL_0000809	2d-ftu-thymus-th	1	CT		
Thymus	UBERON:00023 #FTUThymusLoi #2DRefObjects	Double_Positive	Double_Positive	double-positive,	CL:0000809	http://purl.obolibrary.org/obo/CL_0000809	2d-ftu-thymus-th	1	CT		
Thymus	UBERON:00023 #FTUThymusLoi #2DRefObjects	Double_Positive	Double_Positive	double-positive,	CL:0000809	http://purl.obolibrary.org/obo/CL_0000809	2d-ftu-thymus-th	1	CT		

Figure 6. Sample of a crosswalk table mapped to the illustration.

References and Resources

- Rachel Bajema. (2022). Creating 2D Illustrations for Functional Tissue Units (FTU) <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6703107> (v1.1.0). Zenodo.
- de Bono, B., Grenon, P., Baldock, R., & Hunter, P. (2013). Functional tissue units and their primary tissue motifs in multi-scale physiology. *Journal of biomedical semantics*, 4(1), 22. <https://doi.org/10.1186/2041-1480-4-22>.

Human Reference Atlas

Standard Operating Procedure

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Glossary

ASCT+B Tables: Anatomical Structures, Cell Types and Biomarkers (ASCT+B) Tables are authored by multiple experts across many consortia. Tables capture the partonomy of anatomical structures, cell types and major biomarkers (e.g., gene, protein, lipid or metabolic markers).

Crosswalk: An ontological mapping of terms in the Human Reference Atlas digital objects (e.g., 2/3D reference objects, OMAPs, Azimuth references) to ontology terms in the ASCT+B tables.

Functional tissue unit (FTU): A functional tissue unit is the smallest tissue organization that performs a unique physiologic function and is replicated multiple times in a whole organ.

Scalable Vector Graphics (SVG): A web-friendly vector file format. As opposed to pixel-based raster files like JPEGs, vector files store images via mathematical formulas based on points and lines on a grid.

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